

TOURIST ATTRACTIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Tourist attractions and economic development in Nigeria: An empirical review is the subject of discourse. The study was set to achieve two specific objectives: to determine the relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria and to ascertain the relationship between tourist attractions and rural development in Nigeria. Structured questionnaires were administered to the selected tourist attractions (tourist employees, management, and rural dwellers). Descriptive statistics was adopted to analyze the research questions. The hypotheses were tested using linear regression analysis to obtain the relationship between the variable under review. The findings showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between tourist attractions and the employment rate in Nigeria. It also revealed that tourist attractions are a source of rural development in Nigeria. It was concluded that tourism has tremendously contributed to the growth of relevant services and infrastructure in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommended that government should create a serene environment that has the capacity to enhance destination attractiveness in Nigeria; that funds realized from tourism should be used for development projects, and that more attention should be given to tourism because of its employment opportunities to the jobless youths in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS

Tourist attractions, tourism, employment, rural development, economic development.

Introduction

Tourism plays a tremendous impact in the economic development of many countries, contributing to the growth of relevant services and infrastructure. Thus, the development of tourism affects the progress and prosperity of the national economy. Nigeria is a blessed country with all manners of natural endowment deposited in every parts of the country. Nature has decorated Nigeria as the leading tourist centre in Africa. The landscape which is rich and embellished with natural attractions such vegetation, mangroves, dynamic rocks, mountains, falls, beaches, relics, wildlife etc. Besides, the God-given natural resources, the cultures, customs, and traditions, including their sacred grooves and worship sites, are some of the touristic features that have been abandoned over several decades, which negatively affects the development of the tourism industry.

The oil boom from 1959 till date has been the mainstay of Nigeria economy. The oil is vulnerable to fluctuations in demand and price in the international market which means that Nigerian economy is being controlled by the powers of the international oil cartel. Therefore, the call for full attention on tourism development is imminent because of the dwindling mono-cultural oil economy.

The potentials of tourism in Nigeria spans from 1970's and 1980's but at that period Nigeria's thought were strong in the pursuing of tourism business until the 1990's. From 1990's till date, the potentials for tourism development were glaring and following tourist attractions were developed and explored; Gurara Water Falls, Ikogosi and Wikki warm springs, Mambilla Plateau, Riyom rock formation, Idanre Hills, Zuma Rock, Olumo Rock, Ikom Water Falls, etc. - Ikeja water parks, Snake Island, Ibadan Amusement Centre, Abuja parks and Amusement, Lagos bar beach, Obudu Cattle Ranch, Nicon and Sheraton Hotels, Zaranda Hotels. Etc. - Yankari, New Bussa and Bauchi Game Reserves. Plateau Gardens and Monuments, Kano and Ibadan zoo's, Cross river boat and fishing regatta, Argungu fishing festival etc. - Atilogu Dancers, Kuntigi and Kalangu local guitarists, Yam festival, Gale and Gboya Nupe Tradition, Eyo masquerades, Ekwechi Festival in Ebira Bronze Statutes from Benin, local fan and hat from North, local cloth dyers from China etc. - Dambe and Langa Traditional from North, Circus from China etc. - Varieties of Seminars, conferences, meetings and workshops in hotspot tourist locations across Nigeria (Ndajiya, Shehu, & Yunusa, 2014).

Today, tourism is no longer a leisure but an activity that has captured the attention of economists as a major source of foreign exchange for developing and developed countries, compelling aspiring nations to develop both tourist sites, standardize operations and improve infrastructures such electricity, airports, rail, roads, seaport, that support tourism. Unlike oil that is non-renewable, and which at best employs less than 2% of the population, tourism on the other hand, is an inclusive, sustainable, labour-intensive industry, engaging both skill and unskilled labour. It has the potential to create more jobs per unit of investment than the oil industry (Eneji, Odey, & Bullus, 2016).

Environmentally, tourism if properly harnessed, can serve as a tool for safeguarding and protecting the environment: the ecosystem, preserving historical, archaeological and religious artifacts, and exciting the practice of local cultures, folklore, traditions, arts and crafts, and cuisine, (Francois & Don, 1980; Lawrence et al.1988; Toh & Linda, 1990).

Economically, tourism is a source of revenue to Federal, State & Local governments as well as the private investors if properly organized and managed. It has the capacity to increase the foreign exchange and returns on investment (for investors), taxation (taxing the tourist centres, tourist products), and agriculture and fisheries products emanating from tourism activities (Frangialli 2006). At the same time, tourism serves as the sources of employment which is not only to the urban areas but also rural communities that host tourist sites and monuments. The practical example is that of Obudu Mountain Resort in Cross Rivers State providing source of livelihoods for the local communities surrounding the resort.

Tourism today, has become one of the engine-room for growth of Nigerian economy with a contribution of 3.20 per cent to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing 2.70 per cent of total employment in 2013 (WTTC, 2014). Tourism industry contribution to GDP, according to World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) is envisaged to rise by 6.1 per cent per annum from 2014 to 2024. Nigeria tourism sector is therefore growing, and

it is capable of generating employment and earning large amount of foreign exchange that rivalled agriculture and petroleum sectors.

The benefits of tourism are enormous: economic growth, promotion of peace, development of human resources, and reducing of poverty level, etc. However, serious challenges associated with tourist attractions include the poor transport system whereby roads are unmotorable and kidnapping for ransoms have inhabit the growth of tourism in Nigeria. It is also on record that religious extremist makes countries like the United States of America, United Kingdom, some Asian countries to issue travel warnings to its citizens travelling to Nigeria, and to avoid certain cities in Nigeria when travelling becomes necessary. The aim of this current study was to establish the relationship between tourist attractions and economic development in Nigeria using empirical review approach. The specific objectives include.

- (i) To determine the relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria
- (ii) To ascertain the association between tourist attractions and rural development in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept Tourism

The United Nation World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2015) defined tourism as the activities of persons traveling to and residing in places outside their homes for not less than one consecutive year for the purposes of leisure, business and other related issues to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited.

Gilbert (1990) posited that tourism is a kind of recreation which entails travelling to an unfamiliar destination or community for a short-term period in order to get leisure. This experience usually involves travelling for holiday, excursions, leaves, sabbatical leaves, etc.

According to ProencaandSoukiazis (2005), tourism is determined by a several factors. Among these factors, income is recognized as the major determinant of tourism. They asserted that the demand for and length of stay are directly related to income of potential traveler and inversely related to the domestic cost of living.

Exchange rate is another factor that determines the demand for tourism. It is the price of tourism generating countries currency in relation to the currency of the inbound country. Tourism demand depends on its own price (cost of journey), price of alternative goods and services as well as the general price level of the domestic market. Proenca and Soukiazis (2005) explained that increase in domestic prices of the destination country influenced by exchange rate tend to discourage tourist to move to such destination and can relocate to a cheaper competing places.

Investment climate in the destination country is also an influential factor of tourist attraction in such destination. Tekin (2015) identified empirically that political and economic instability in the destination country adversely affect tourism in such destination. Dwyer and Kim (2003) identified trade openness, relative prices, and consumer prices as important factors explaining tourism demand in a destination.

History of Development of Tourism in Nigeria

The history of tourism in Nigeria started in 1959 when the colonial master setup an Adhoc Advisory Committee on the establishment and promotion of tourism in the country. This committee recommended the establishment of the Nigerian Tourist Association (NTA). The NTA established in 1962 was comprised of government representatives, private individuals and organizations (Anand, 1997: 160). The NTA was a private, voluntary, and non-profit making organization was assisted by the government with funds to shoulder the responsibility of developing and promoting tourism in the country. In 1964, the association joined the International Union of Official Travel Organizations (IUOTO), which metamorphosed into World Tourist Organization (WTO) (Ukpanah, 1991:1). After so many years of failures, the Federal Military Government changed the nomenclature from Nigeria Tourist Association to Nigerian Tourist Board with Decree No. 54 of 1976.

In 1989, the Federal Military Government reorganized the Nigerian Tourist Board and created a department for tourism in the Ministry of Trade and renamed it the Ministry of Trade and Tourism (Ukpanah, 1991: 3). Six zones were established with their headquarters to cover the whole country and later state headquarters were also established for better administration (Ukpanah, 1991: 3). State governments were also ordered to create similar ministries and local governments were ordered to create committees for tourism. Throughout this period, tourism development and policies were formulated and executed by the three tiers of government with the help of the Nigerian Tourist Board, which has offices in every state. On 14 December 1992, Decree 81 was used to establish the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation, which replaced the Nigerian Tourist Board (Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation Decree No 81, 1992). From 1957, when the ad hoc committee was established, up to the creation of the Ministry of Trade and Tourism, it was a story of failures as far as the Nigerian tourism industry is concerned, despite all the opportunities and potentials that are abundant in the country. Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation is still the government agency responsible for the development of tourism industry in Nigeria.

Tourist Centres in Nigeria

	Location
1. The Ibeno Beach Ibeno,	Akwa Ibom State
2. Obudu Mountain Resort Obudu,	Cross River State
3. Ngwo Pine Forest Ngwo,	Enugu State
4. Awhum Waterfall Awhum,	Enugu State
5. Arochukwu Long juju slave route	Abia State
6. The Giant Footprint of Ukhuseoke Owan,	Edo State
7. Port Harcourt Tourist Beach	River State
8. Gashaki-Gumpti National park	Taraba State
9. Alok Ikom Monoliths	Cross River State
10. Isaac Boro Garden Park	River State
11. The Tinapa free zone and resort	Cross River State
12. Osun-Osogbo Grove	Osun State
13. The Emotan Statue	Edo State
14. The Royal palace of Oba of Benin	Edo State
15. Sukur cultural landscape	Madageli, Adamawa State
16. Queen Amina's wall	Zaria, Kaduna State
17. Surame cultural landscape	Surame, Sokoto State
18. Oban Hills	Cross River State
19. Oke-Idanre Hills	Oke-Idanre, Ondo State
20. Ogbnike Caves	Enugu State
21. Ancient Kano city walls	Kano, Kano State
22. Coconut Beach	Badagry, Lagos State
23. Bar Beach	Victoria Island, Lagos
24. Millennium Park	Maitama, Abuja
25. Nana living history museum	Wari, Delta State
26. The Ancient Nok settlement	Jaba, Kaduna State
27. New Afrika Shrine	Ikeja, Lagos State
28. Abuja Arts and crafts village	Abuja
29. Kainji National Park	Niger State
30. Yankari National park	Bauchi State

Source: Ministry of Information, Culture and Tourism, 2016

Tourism and Economic Development in Nigeria

Tourism has significant impact on a destination's development. The term economic development is the process that affects all facets of economy which implies that the economic well-being and quality of life of a nation, region, local community, or an individual are upgraded in line with the objectives of the government.

Tourism is considered the driving force for economic growth and also creates foreign exchange and boosts employment opportunities and local incomes for rural people. Numerous studies in different underdeveloped nations around the world have found a significant correlation between tourism and economic expansion (Steiner, 2006; Croes & Vanegas, 2008).

Tourism as a tool for diversifying the economies of many countries (Ayeni, 2012). This has supported the services sector and created a significant link with the Nigerian economy, promoting new employment opportunities and creating new sources of revenue. However, developed countries have a higher rate of global tourism compared to less developed countries. Again, there are many opportunities for less developed countries to benefit from this industry.

Manwa (2012) argued that in order for tourism to be sustainable for society, the society must benefit economically and financially from it and it will allow them to protect and maintain popular tourist areas. This is also emphasized by Smith (2007) that the economic advantages of tourism depend on the country's ability to offer the required facilities.

Scholars have shown a direct link between international trade (especially export expansion) and economic growth (Bahmani-Oskooee 1993; Chow, 1987; and Marin, 1992). The authors have seen a strong correlation between international trade and economic growth and also a strong correlation between exports and economic growth. In addition, tourism extensions are linked to economic development. However, export-oriented economic growth has led to a decline in tourism income. Finally, sustainable tourism promotion strategies may not be as effective as decision makers perceive if no direct link is found between tourism development and economic development, because it generally occurs when tourism development has a positive impact on the economy (Smith, 2007).

Tourism is one of the facilitator to the development of road infrastructure that improves the quality of life of people living within the tourist centers. It is indisputable to prove that road infrastructure is an important representation of the tourist infrastructure that directly affects the tourist centres that attracts visitors. In the words of Kaul (1985) transport plays an important role in the successful creation and development of new tourist centres as well as in the healthy development of existing ones. The provision of proper transport has turned the dead centers of tourist interest into active and prosperous places that attract crowds. Indeed, the road network system performs the task of connecting areas with each other, as well as with tourist attractions which becomes the factor for business competitiveness in the tourist areas. International visitors often go to destinations where the road network systems are motorized.

Prideaux (2000, p. 53) argues that if the ability of tourists to travel to preferred destinations is hampered by the poor road network, there is every reason they can look for better alternative destinations. Therefore, the government's commitment to building better roads leading to tourist centers is important. Then investing in transport infrastructure development has been an issue for governments for many years.

Theoretical Foundations

Theory of Modernization: Theory of modernization was propounded Rostow Winton in 1954 when he was developing strategies for building stadia. It was coined Rostow's theory of growth and development. This theory expatiates the various strata that are involved in developing tourism projects until they become generally acceptable for the purpose of business. Modernization is very necessary for the systematic and transformative change of environment. One of the principal applications of modernization theory has been in economic field and public policy. Tourist industries are an economic field that focused on economic development. The economic theory of modernization hinges on the primary five levels of development as follows: the traditional society (pre-industrial), preconditions for take-off, the take-off process, the drive maturity and high mass consumption (Rostow, 1990).

The tenet of Rostow's theory of growth and development is that there is a natural inertia that must subdue before self-sustained development emanate. They include built up transport, investment enhanced organization and production in agriculture and increase in imports particularly capital. These three factors are seen as the preconditions for take-off. The application of this theory shows the sequential process for tourism project

development. The standard stated in this development process aids in the provision of infrastructure to the people, and social amenities to the sites and its environs, and provide the tourists coming and interacting communities with good roads, communication network, banks, hospitals and other strategies to sustain and maintain the site.

Empirical Review and Hypotheses Development

Tourism and Employment in Nigeria

Scholars have diverse perceptions concerning how tourist industries contribute to economic development of Nigeria through expansion of gross domestic products and employment rate. A number of academics have the same opinion on the important parts played by tourism in Nigeria and how positively impacts on growth of the economy

Employment is the agreement between two parties (employer and employee), usually based on a terms and conditions of service, where one party, which may be a company (employer) or other entity (employee) (*Dakin & Armstrong, 1989*). Employees work in return for remuneration, which can be in the form of hourly wages, weekly payment or monthly salary depending on the arrangement. In this aspect, it is private, corporate or government that engages the personnel to work with consolidate agreement. Hence, we have self-employment, those who are working and getting paid by themselves. In tourist industries, there are qualified personnel who are engaged in the day-to-day activities of the industries. Again, remember that tourism involves tourist attractions, guest house, hotels, motel and government agency – those who work for these listed organizations are paid monthly.

Manzoor, Wei, Asif, Hag, and Hafiz (2019) carried out a study on the contribution of sustainable tourism to economic growth and employment in Pakistan. Among others, their findings shows that globally, tourism plays an important role in boosting a nation's economy and also an increase in tourism flow brings positive economic outcomes to the nations, especially in gross domestic product (GDP) and employment opportunities.

Eneji, Odey, and Bullus, (2016) investigated the diversification of Nigeria's economy and the impact of tourism on sustainable development in Nigeria. Their study showed that tourism has significant and positive impact on the economy, but the subsector is still under-invested and under-utilized. That tourism has direct impact on employment, income, infrastructure and standard of living.

The impact of tourist attractions and service organisations to employment generation in Nigeria is still very insignificant as compared to the expectation (Yusuff and Akinde, 2015). The ratio of the sector to total employment ranged from 4.9% in 2005 and zigzag in the subsequent years to fall to 2.70% in 2014. Wall and Mathieson (2006) asserted that tourism should be encouraged more for the fact that it may contribute to the well-being of local people in destination areas and less for the reason that it is good for the tourist industry per se. From the foregoing we hypothesise that:

H1: There is significant relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria.

Tourism and Rural Development in Nigeria

Travel & Tourism contributed to the construction and building roads, hotels, motels and markets in the tourist areas. Along with transport infrastructure, communications infrastructure also plays a vital role in attracting tourists. Pearce and Wu (2015) show that transport, tourism facilities and communications are the main components of infrastructure. Telecommunication industry also situated their Mask within the vicinity for effective communication for tourist, thereby positively impacting on the development of rural areas.

Raina (2005) believes that the development of tourist centre calls for construction of motorable road to the location. This serves as a source of development to those areas, because it enhances their livelihood and standard of living. In the rural areas most of their roads are not tarred road, so it is tourism that brings about this development.

Currently, empirical studies has shown the role of transport and communications infrastructure in attracting tourists, with the result that transport and communications infrastructure are proving to be important factors influencing the number of tourists visiting (Khadaroo and Seetanah 2007b). Transport infrastructure is an important determinant of tourist inflows to a destination (Khadaroo and Seetanah 2008), the transport chapter has contributed positively to the number of tourist arrivals both in the short and long term (Seetanah and Khadaroo 2009). Transport infrastructure that promotes the tourism industry (Yu 2016). Therefore, infrastructure and transport are important elements of the tourism supply chain (Ghaderi et al. 2018). The development of transport infrastructure, such as highways, and train stations, has a positive impact on overnight stays in all types of accommodation (Ouariti and Jebrane 2020). In addition, Tang (2020) argues that improving transport infrastructure is an important element of trade facilitation and that trade facilitation has improved the efficiency of the inbound tourism market, especially the infrastructure index (Tang, 2020).

Yusuff, and Akinde, (2015) studies titled “determined the impact of tourism development and economic growth nexus: The Nigeria’s experience”. Their observations revealed a unilateral causality and positive long-run between tourism development and economic growth. The tourism-led growth is also thus confirmed for Nigeria. The study recommends adequate security, increase investment in infrastructure and tourist centres to boost tourism activities in the country.

Akighir, andAteata, (2017) understudied the implication of tourism-economic growth nexus in Nigeria: implications for the economic recovery and growth plan. Their findings revealed that, tourism development has positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria both in the short and long-run. Based on their findings it was concluded that the government can use the enormous tourist potentials in the country to achieve her economic recovery and growth plan (ERGP) in the wake of dwindling oil prices.

Raina (2005) considers that, together with transport, hotels, motels and restaurants are the natural elements for tourist infrastructural development in the rural areas. Meanwhile, the Tourism and Transport Forum (2012) points out that hotels are an important component of the social infrastructure of tourism. From the foregoing we hypothesise that:

H2: There is significant relationship between tourist attractions and rural development in Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population sample of 2500 was adopted for the study. The population sample was subjected to Taro Yamane Formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N)(e)^2}$$

Where : n = sample size required; N = no. of sample population; e=allowable error (5%)

Substituting the value of 2500 into the equation

$$n = \frac{2500}{(1 + 2500)(0.05)^2} ; n = 344.82; \approx 345 \text{ (sample size)}$$

However, this study used convenience sampling technique to choose 69 from the selected 5 tourist attractions in Nigeria: (i). Obudu Mountain Resort Obudu, Cross River State; (ii). Awlum Waterfall Awlum, Enugu State; (iii). Port Harcourt Tourist Beach, River State; (iv). The Tinapa free zone and resort, and (v) Ogbunike Caves, Enugu State. Structured questionnaires were administered to the selected tourist attractions (tourist employees, managements, and rural dwellers). The descriptive statistics was adopted to analyse the research questions. The hypotheses were tested using linear regression analysis to obtain the relationship between the variable under review.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Data presentation, N= 345

S/No	Tourist Attractions	Administered questionnaire	Accessible questionnaire	Inaccessible questionnaire
1	Obudu Mountain Resort Obudu, Cross River State	69	63(91.30%)	6(8.70%)
2	Awhum Waterfall Awhum, Enugu State	69	59 (85.51%)	10(14.49%)
3	Port Harcourt Tourist Beach, River State	69	62(89.86%)	7(10.14%)
4	The Tinapa free zone and resort, Cross River State	69	64(92.75%)	5(7.25%)
5	Ogbunike Caves, Enugu State	69	62(89.86%)	7(10.14%)
	Total	345	310	34

The questionnaire was administered to tourist attractions and rural community dwellers to obtain their responses. The researcher retrieved the instrument the next day and the following results were ascertained as contained in Table 1.

Research question 1: What is the relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria?

Table 2: Statistics of Tourist Attractions and employment rate in Nigeria

		Office employment	Food vendors	Petty traders	Transport business
N	Valid	310	310	310	310
	Missing	0	0	0	0
	Mean	1.9258	1.8645	1.9742	2.0290
	Std. Deviation	1.00370	.94562	1.03310	1.06843

Table 2 contained the descriptive result of research question 1, revealing that tourist attractions contributed to employment at mean and standard deviation for office employment at $x=1.93$ and $std =1.00$; food vendors opportunities at $x = 1.86$ and $std 0.95$, petty trader at $x = 1.97$ and $std 1.03$ and transport business at $x = 2.03$ and $std 1.07$.

Table 3: Statistics of Tourist Attractions and rural development in Nigeria

		Lifeline rural development	Providing jobs	Supporting rural business	Protecting natural cultural heritage
N	Valid	310	310	310	310
	Missing	0	0	0	0
	Mean	2.1097	1.7484	1.8710	1.8161
	Std. Deviation	1.06165	.89293	.95334	.94940

Table 3 contained the descriptive result of research question 2, maintaining that tourist attractions contributed to rural development at mean and standard deviation of $x=2.11$ and $std =1.06$ for lifeline rural development respondents; providing jobs at $x = 1.75$ and $std 0.89$, supporting rural business at $x = 1.87$ and $std 0.95$ and protecting natural cultural heritage at $x = 1.82$ and $std 0.95$.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is positive and significant relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria.

Table 4: Linear regression analysis of tourist attractions and employment rate

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.971 ^a	.944	.943	.22502	.944	5149.120	1	308	.000	.353

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tourist attractions

b. Dependent Variable: Employment rate

Table 4 contained the linear regression analysis output of hypothesis 1. The result indicated correlation coefficient r , 0.971 and p -value=.000 is lower than the 5% significant level. Therefore, the hypothesis was supported which means that there is positive and significant relationship between tourist attractions and employment rate in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no positive and significant relationship between tourist attractions and rural development in Nigeria.

Table 5: Linear regression analysis of tourist attractions and rural development

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.893 ^a	.797	.797	.40269	.797	1211.367	1	308	.000	.094

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tourist attractions

b. Dependent Variable: Rural development

Table 5 contained the linear regression analysis output of hypothesis 2. The result indicated the correlation coefficient r , 0.893 and p -value =.000 which is lower than the 5% significant level. Therefore, the hypothesis was supported which implies that there is positive and significant relationship between tourist attractions and rural development rate in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study deals with the tourist attractions and economic development in Nigeria. The results from the finding revealed that tourist attractions are agents for employment in Nigeria, These visitor attractions have provided employment for the jobless Nigerian youths in the urban and rural areas. The proliferation of hotels within the tourist attractions have necessitated the opportunities in those areas. However, another finding showed that tourist attractions have positive and significant relationship with rural development in Nigeria. It is obvious that most of the tourist attractions are located in the rural areas. This have initiated development in all areas ranging from provision of social amenities, such as rural electrification, motorable roads, potable water, health centres and security network for securing lives and properties of the tourist and the dwellers.

Scholars like Manzoor, Wei, Asif, Hag, and Hafiz (2019) discovered that tourism enhances economic growth and employment in Pakistan which the present also adumbrated. Again, works of Eneji, Odey, and Bullus, (2016) on diversification of Nigeria's economy and the impact of tourism on sustainable development in Nigeria have the same results with the present study. Also, the findings of Yusuff, and Akinde, (2015) on the impact of tourism development and economic growth nexus: The Nigeria's experience showed similar results with the current work.

Conclusion

Tourism has tremendously contributed to the economic development of Nigeria. The development of tourism affects the progress and prosperity of the nation's economy. It is no longer a leisure but an activity that has captured the attention of economists as a major source of foreign exchange for developing and developed countries. The employment rate and rural development has been heavily impacted through tourism development this calls for more attention in tourism sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made.

- (i) That government should create a serene environment that have the capacity to enhance destination attractiveness.
- (ii) That government should judiciously use the proceeds obtained from tourism for developmental projects.
- (iii) That more attention should be given to tourism because of its employment opportunities and rural development index.

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